

RURAL TOURISM IN THE FEDERATION OF BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA -THE CHARACTERISTICS OF DEMAND OF USERS OF ETHNIC VILLAGE SERVICES

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Abstract: *The development of rural tourism, in addition to contributing to the economic empowerment of the rural population, also contributes to the strengthening of local and regional economies, as well as the global economy. The most important consequence of the development of rural tourism in the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina is the progress of rural communities and the improvement of the socioeconomic status of the rural population. So, the aim of this paper is to examine the attitudes and preferences of visitors about the current tourist offer within rural areas (ethnic villages) and determine characteristics of demand and the satisfaction of visitors. The results of the survey show that in most cases, respondents visit ethnic villages once every six months or less. The key motives for choosing a destination are healthy food and enjoying national specialties, spending time with family and friends, escaping stress and crowds, rest and relaxation, and natural resources. Visitors to ethnic villages in the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina are mostly satisfied or absolutely satisfied with the overall offer of rural tourism.*

Key words: *rural tourism, the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina, local economic development, tourist satisfaction.*

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1. Introduction

Tourism is a very complex and important economic category with extremely dynamic development and rapid qualitative and quantitative changes. It can be said that tourism is an “opportunity” that can transform a certain area into a country with a good quality of life and a high standard of living (Shkodra, 2024). Rural tourism includes tourism of rural areas with all activities that are carried out and realized in that area as part of the offer. The development of rural tourism is a relatively new phenomenon compared to traditional rural economic activities. Ethnic tourism, as a type of rural tourism, includes typically visiting ethnic villages and native homes, involvement in ethnic events and festivals, eating local food, watching traditional dances and ceremonies and shopping souvenirs. Because of the growing importance of rural tourism in the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina, especially ethnic tourism, and its impact on economic growth and development, we have chosen topic related to rural tourism and users of ethnic village services with focus on characteristics of demand. We find it very interesting to analyze, to see which part of mentioned services has the greatest impact on the level of tourist satisfaction. Our goal in Bosnia and Herzegovina, from a tourism perspective, should be better tourist offer and satisfied tourists. We consider that we have a good basis to achieve it. And this also makes our topic important and interesting.

The aim of this paper is to examine the attitudes and preferences of visitors about the current tourist offer within rural areas (ethnic villages) and determine characteristics of demand and the satisfaction of visitors. There are not many studies (we didn't find any in our country) which treat the impact of rural tourism on tourist satisfaction and that's why we consider that our paper will give a contribution to this field of research. There are some studies in Bosnia and Herzegovina (Peštek and Tufo, 2018; Knežević et al., 2017; Krajinović et al., 2011) but they mostly deal with rural tourism, in general, and tourist satisfaction isn't prior such as within our research, and that's the main difference. There are some similar studies in Croatia (Mesić et al., 2021; Škaberna, 2017; Gojak, 2016; Piskač, 2016) and, of course, other studies (Kastenholz and Santos, 2014) and (Kastenholz and Lima, 2011) and we will refer to this later, within discussion.

If visitors are satisfied with their tourism experience, they will stay, reducing the village's economic income. Conversely, if visitors are happy with the tourism experience, it can improve their reputation and attract more visitors. (Sukaris, 2024). A satisfied tourist will return to a destination if he/she is satisfied with its offer or will be a good promoter for potential tourists of the observed destinations. Therefore, the rural tourism offer enriches its contents and increases the quality of services to satisfy its tourists. This certainly has a further effect on economic development, in the sense that local communities with diverse tourism offer invest in community infrastructure, strive to improve their services, and invest in education of labor force who will be able to meet the needs of tourists. The content of this paper includes literature review, methodology, research results and conclusion remarks. Combination of desk (relevant publications) and field research method (survey questionnaire) was used as data sources. The findings of this paper confirm the following: development of rural tourism has a significant effect on tourist satisfaction, tourist offers within ethnic villages should be more diverse if we want more visitors and more visitors (tourists) will bring stronger economic development.

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2. Literature review

Rural tourism is the fastest growing segment of tourism and that's why the tourism industry will have to take seriously its impact on the environment, culture, society and economy. (Gašić et al, 2015). Probably, the most widely cited paper in the 1994 issue remains Lane's consideration entitled 'What is rural tourism?'. His analysis of the characteristics of rural areas and his 'typology' of rural tourism are referred to in all subsequent key publications on the subject in the English language. Rural tourism is tourism that takes place in rural areas, characterized by low population density and open space, small settlements with less than 10,000 inhabitants and land used mainly for farms, forestry and natural areas. (Lane, 1994) Rural tourism promotes cultural diversity, the preservation of national heritage, the appreciation of the lifestyle and traditions of indigenous peoples, and respect for their privacy and dignity." (Alexandrov, 2005)

Rural tourism is defined as the touristic valorization of agricultural areas, natural resources, cultural heritage, rural settlements, local traditional customs and products through specially designed tourist products that reflect the identity of the area and meet the needs of guests in terms of accommodation, food and beverage services, recreation and activities, animation and other services, with the aim of sustainable local development, but also providing adequate answers to the needs of today's guests within the newly created relations between urban and rural area (OECD, 1994). If we carefully read this definition, we can conclude that satisfied guests are an important part of rural tourism, in some cases the most important. So, if we use our resources within rural tourism properly, we will have satisfied tourists who will promote our potential, and we can also achieve higher level of local economic development.

It can be said that rural tourism represents a relatively new tourist activity that aims to return people to traditional values and the natural environment. At the same time, it is important to point out that rural tourism did not arise only as a need for new tourist facilities, but as a need for preservation and revitalization, actually for reviving and giving new added value to the inherited heritage and authentic promotion of traditional knowledge and skills through the organization of an attractive and original tourist offer (Demonja, 2012). Demand for rural tourism is related directly to the particular characteristics of rural areas, and it is assumed that the principal motivation for visiting the countryside is to experience rurality. (Sharpley and Lesley, 2004)

We can notice that there is no unique definition of rural tourism but all of them emphasize importance of rural environment and traditional values, and interaction between tourists and local population. In the Federation Bosnia and Herzegovina, there are already a lot of guesthouses, rural households, camps, vineyard houses, mountain huts and ethnic villages that provide rural tourism services: sports and recreational content, such as hunting, fishing and rafting, then attending or participating in the work of growing food and caring for animals, horse riding, visiting important localities nearby, etc.

The results of the survey question confirm that visitors are not sufficiently familiar with the offer of rural tourism in FBiH and its development. Similar results were obtained in the research of rural tourism in neighboring Croatia according to Mesić et al (2021) and Škaberna (2017). The results also point out the fact that the key motives for choosing a destination are healthy food and enjoyment of national specialties, spending time with

family and friends, escaping stress and crowds, rest and relaxation. Similar results were obtained by Mesić et al. (2021), Gojak (2016) and Piskač (2016).

The benefits and impacts of tourism in the local economy are closely interrelated with other sectors and actors responsible for the economic development of the country (Laidler, 2012). In addition, community knowledge and support for tourism greatly influence the development of competitive advantage of rural tourism destinations. Rural tourism has been recognized as essential for improving local welfare and living standards (Aliman et al., 2016).

The importance of tourism and the motives of travel are the starting point for studying attitudes as variables in visitor behavior. Scientific literature reveals different types of motives and behavior, depending on the type of tourism that is practiced, so depending on whether it is about conventional or about rural tourism (Porutiu et al., 2021) Pizam, Neumann, and Reichel (1978) define tourist satisfaction as “a collection of tourists’ attitudes about specific domains in their vacation experience”. Villages must build excellent service quality for better satisfaction by Uzir et al., (2021). According to Caber (2012) high service quality and customer satisfaction are appropriate determinants of a destination’s competitiveness. In a study conducted by Ragavan et al. (2014) and Valduga et al. (2020), they determined tourist perception and satisfaction towards a tourist destination by assessing numerous destination attributes involving accommodations and food, attractions, climate and image, products, accessibility, culture, communities, and price.

According to Asmelash & Kumar (2019), tourist satisfaction levels are significantly affected by destination attributes. If tourists are pleased with the attributes of the destination, it can be expected that their satisfaction levels will be high and that they probably will be back one day and promote tourist destinations within social media. Some research defines visitor satisfaction as a product or service experience obtained by comparing expected and perceived performance (Paulose and Shakeel, 2022). When it comes to visitor satisfaction with overall rural tourism in FBiH, most of respondents are satisfied or absolutely satisfied with the offer. Similar results were obtained by the authors Mesić et al. (2021) and Kastenholz and Lima (2011).

3. Research methodology

In view of the research objectives, the collection of primary data was carried out using the research technique of the survey questionnaire. The survey was conducted during the period April-October 2024. The survey was conducted among visitors to ethnic villages in FBiH. The personal survey was conducted on a sample of 45 respondents.

The survey questionnaire consisted of 9 closed and open-ended questions, which was created in accordance with a similar survey conducted in the neighboring country of Croatia (Mesić et al., 2021) while respecting the slight differences and limited resources of the project for which this survey was conducted. For the two last mentioned questions, respondents expressed their satisfaction with the quality of the visited ethnic village on a 5-level Likert scale, as well as the assessment of the development of rural tourism in Bosnia and Herzegovina. One group of questions in the survey questionnaire related to socio-demographic characteristics: gender, age, personal income and origin.

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The results of the survey were processed using the statistical software package SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences). Frequency and distribution were used for the analysis of the results. All obtained data are presented in the tables.

4. Research results

As previously emphasized, the survey was conducted on a sample of 45 respondents in selected ethnic villages in FBiH.

Of the total number of respondents, 42.2% were men, and 57.8% were women, which can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1: Gender of respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Men	19	42.2
Women	26	57.8
Total	45	100.0

Source: Independent work of the author

Visitors to ethnic villages in the FBiH are mostly young and middle-aged people, more precisely respondents between the ages of 21 and 31, and 43 and 53, cumulatively occupying 57.8% of the total number of respondents, which can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2: Age of respondents

Age	Frequency	Percent
less than 20 years	3	6.7
21-31	13	28.9
32-42	9	20.0
43-53	13	28.9
over 53 years	7	15.6
Total	45	100.0

Source: Independent work of the author

Domestic tourists are mostly present in the ethnic villages of the FBiH, more precisely 84.4% of respondents included in this research come from BiH (table 3).

Table 3: Country of origin of respondents

Country	Frequency	Percent
BiH	38	84.4
Srbija	2	4.4
EU countries	5	11.1
Total	45	100.0

Source: Independent work of the author

When it comes to the material status of the respondents, in table 4. it can be seen that 64.4% of the respondents have a monthly income in the interval 1001-2001 KM, 24.4% have an income in the interval 2002-3002, 8.9% have an income over 3002 KM, while 2.2% of the respondents have an income of less than 1000 KM. From the above, it can be concluded that, for the most part, tourists in the ethnic villages of FBiH are with medium incomes.

Table 4: Monthly income

Monthly income	Frequency	Percent
less than 1000 KM	1	2.2
1001-2001	29	64.4
2002-3002	11	24.4
over 3002	4	8.9
Total	45	100.0

Source: Independent work of the author

Tourists visit ethnic villages in FBiH mostly once every six months (35.6%) or even less often, once a year (22.2%) and other (24.4%), which can be seen in table 5.

Table 5: Intensity of visits to ethnic villages

Intensity	Frequency	Percent
once a week	3	6.7
once a month	5	11.1
once every six months	16	35.6
once a year	10	22.2
a rest	11	24.4
Total	45	100.0

Source: Independent work of the author

The conducted research showed that in 62.2% of cases, tourists are satisfied and absolutely satisfied with the rural tourist offer in FBiH (cumulative view, table 6.). 31.1% of respondents do not have an opinion about the satisfaction with the tourist offer of ethnic villages in FBiH, which is expected considering the intensity of visits to them.

Table 6: Satisfaction with the rural tourist offer

Satisfaction	Frequency	Percent
absolutely satisfied	8	17.8
satisfied	20	44.4
neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	14	31.1
dissatisfied	3	6.7
Total	45	100.0

Source: Independent work of the author

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Among ethnic villages in FBiH, tourists like the natural resources that are represented in them the most (31.1%, table 7.). In addition to the natural resources, tourists are also satisfied with the food and the friendliness of the staff in ethnic villages. 60% of the answers to this survey question were "other", which means that tourists like more things in ethnic villages, so in addition to the natural resources, they also like the gastronomic offer or the friendliness of the staff.

Table 7: Factors that attract tourists to ethnic villages

Satisfaction factors	Frequency	Percent
food	3	6.7
natural resources	14	31.1
the friendliness of the staff	1	2.2
the rest	27	60.0
Total	45	100.0

Source: Independent work of the author

Respondents included in this research assessed that the degree of development of rural tourism in FBiH is good in 46.7% of cases (table 8.), that is, very good and excellent in 22.2% of cases cumulatively. 28.9% of tourists believe that the degree of development of rural tourism in FBiH is sufficient. These results indicate that providers of rural tourism in FBiH have a lot of things for advancement in terms of exploiting available natural resources, as well as specialization and a more comprehensive business management policy.

Table 8: Degree of development of rural tourism in FBiH

Development of rural tourism	Frequency	Percent
excellent	2	4.4
very good	8	17.8
good	21	46.7
enough	13	28.9
insufficient	1	2.2
Total	45	100.0

Source: Independent work of the author

The results of the conducted research also show the great importance of agritourism within the framework of rural tourism in FBiH. As many as 80% of respondents (table 9.), cumulatively, consider that agritourism is an important and absolutely essential segment of rural tourism in FBiH, which can also be a useful development guideline for managers of ethnic villages in FBiH.

Table 9: Importance of agritourism

Importance of agritourism	Frequency	Percent
it absolutely matters to me	11	24.4
it matters to me	25	55.6
it is neither important nor unimportant to me	7	15.6
it is absolutely irrelevant to me	2	4.4
Total	45	100.0

Source: Independent work of the author

5. Discussion

The aim of this work was to determine the attitudes and preferences of visitors related to rural tourism in FBiH, and to determine visitor satisfaction with the offer of ethnic villages in FBiH.

The results of the research show that respondents, in the largest number of cases (82.2% in total), visit ethnic villages once every six months or less often. The above leads to the conclusion that visitors are not sufficiently familiar with the offer of rural tourism in FBiH. The results of the survey question related to the degree of development of rural tourism in FBiH also agree with this. Namely, 46.7% of respondents evaluated the degree of development with an average rating of "good". Similar results were obtained in the research of rural tourism in neighboring Croatia. Namely, most visitors are partially familiar with the offer of rural tourism in Dubrovnik-Neretva County (Mesić et al, 2021), as well as in Krapina Zagorje County (Škaberna, 2017). Such research results indicate that the offer of rural tourism neither in FBiH nor in Croatia is sufficiently promoted. Because of the above, more significant investments are needed in various forms of marketing, and especially promotional activities, in accordance with the characteristics of demand in the markets observed.

The conducted research points to the fact that the key motives for choosing a destination are healthy food and enjoyment of national specialties, spending time with family and friends, escaping stress and crowds, rest and relaxation. Similar results were obtained by Mesić et al. (2021) for the area of Dubrovnik-Neretva County, and Gojak (2016) for the city of Makarska and its surroundings. Also, Piskač (2016) during the research of rural tourism in Croatian Zagorje determined that the key motives of this type of tourism are rest and getting to know the traditional gastronomy of the region. The results of research on rural tourism in FBiH also show that an important factor for choosing a destination is natural wealth, that is, agrotourism is important or absolutely important for 80% of respondents. Similar results were obtained by Kastenholz and Santos (2014) in the area of southern Rio de Grande do Sul (Brazil), where the authors conclude that, in addition to vacation, a very important factor in rural tourism is proximity to nature, peace, quiet, learning about animals.

When it comes to visitor satisfaction with overall rural tourism in FBiH, 62.2% of respondents are satisfied or absolutely satisfied with the offer. Similar results were obtained by the authors Mesić et al. (2021) for the Dubrovnik-Neretva County, where the average rating of the visitors for the offer was 3.9, while Kastenholz and Lima (2011) in the research conducted for Portugal determined that the satisfaction rating of the offer of the visitors was 4.3.

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6. Conclusion

Rural tourism is a form of tourism that goes beyond city breaks and popular tourist attractions. It means traveling to natural places that are non-urbanised, often rely on agriculture and with low populations, such as villages and cottages, homestays, farms, and ranches or eco lodges. It is related to ethical and sustainable tourism, travelling off the beaten path, outdoor activities and sports and spending time in nature. It has great potential to make the travel more responsible and richer in experience. In developing countries, such as Bosnia and Herzegovina, rural tourism has a great importance. It brings profit directly to families living in rural, otherwise non touristic, distant locations. It also brings opportunities for economic development.

The results of the research show that respondents visit ethnic villages once every six months or less often. The above leads to the conclusion that visitors are not sufficiently familiar with the offer of rural tourism in FBiH. The results of the survey question related to the degree of development of rural tourism in FBiH also agree with this (respondents evaluated the degree of development with an average rating of "good").Based on the above, it can be concluded that stronger promotion of the existing offer is needed, ideally by using new advertising media that have numerous advantages (two-way communication, low usage costs, easier monitoring of the target group). Within the framework of promotional activities, it would be significant to improve cooperation with travel agencies and participate more intensively in travel fairs. When it comes to visitor satisfaction with overall rural tourism in FBiH respondents are satisfied or absolutely satisfied with the offer and they are most satisfied with healthy food and enjoyment of national specialties, spending time with family and friends, escaping stress and crowds, rest and relaxation, and natural wealth.

The conducting research confirmed that the FBiH has the possibilities and potential for further development of rural tourism, but continuous investments in promotion, as well as the development of new products (redesign of existing ones) are needed in order to meet the specifics of tourist demand. The offer of ethnic villages in the FBiH could be significantly enriched by more intensive development of agrotourism. Altogether, it would result in the economic growth of local communities with an inevitable contribution to the overall economy of BiH.

Considering that this research was conducted for the needs of developing a project related to rural tourism in the FBiH, significant limitations in the preparation of the work were the available financial resources for conducting more comprehensive research that would include a larger number of respondents. Also, a significant limitation was the small number of visitors to the ethnic village at the time of conducting the personal survey, as well as the lack of an online database of ethnic village users that would enable an increase in the number of respondents included in this research. The small sample further prevented the creation of a representative econometric model that would establish an appropriate cause-and-effect relationship.

However, regardless of the above limitations, the research provides significant inputs to the rural supply chain in the FBiH for creating business and marketing strategies. The research results can also help local authorities when adopting development strategies for individual regions in the FBiH.

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RURALNI TURIZAM U FEDERACIJI BOSNE I HERCEGOVINE - OBILJEŽJA POTRAŽNJE KORISNIKA USLUGA ETNO SELA

Abstract: *Razvoj ruralnog turizma, osim što doprinosi ekonomskom osnaživanju ruralnog stanovništva, doprinosi i jačanju lokalne i regionalne ekonomije, kao i globalne ekonomije. Najvažnija posljedica razvoja ruralnog turizma u Federaciji Bosne i Hercegovine je napredak ruralnih zajednica i poboljšanje socioekonomskog statusa ruralnog stanovništva. Dakle, cilj ovog rada je da se ispituju stavovi i preferencije posjetilaca vezano za trenutnu turističku ponudu u ruralnim sredinama (etno sela), te utvrde karakteristike potražnje i zadovoljstva posjetilaca. Rezultati istraživanja pokazuju da ispitanici u većini slučajeva posjećuju etno sela svakih šest mjeseci ili rjeđe. Ključni motivi za odabir destinacije su: zdrava hrana i uživanje u nacionalnim specijalitetima, druženje sa porodicom i prijateljima, bijeg od stresa i gužve, odmor i opuštanje, te prirodni resursi. Posjetioci etno sela u Federaciji Bosne i Hercegovine uglavnom su zadovoljni ili apsolutno zadovoljni ukupnom ponudom seoskog turizma.*

Ključne riječi: *ruralni turizam, Federacija Bosne I Hercegovine, lokalni ekonomski razvoj, zadovoljstvo turista.*